

An optimized onboard HVDC controlled rectifier power converter

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Abstract

The concept of Power Optimized More Electric Aircraft, including new electrical architectures, redundancy, integrated and modular avionics, power electronics, new smart sensors and actuators will help achieve more quickly the Green Deal Guidelines promoted by European Commission for reducing pollution and noise. In this new context of electric and hybrid propulsion, the more electric and sustainable aircraft, this work details the design and development procedure of a new AC / DC on-board power converter for aeronautical application. This power converter will be a key component in upcoming aircraft electrical architectures for new power conditioning systems, increasing their safety and reliability. This work will show the procedure to optimize the selection of state-of-the-art components, the use and implementation of advanced electromagnetic compatibility techniques, as well as the implementation of modulation and control algorithms, in order to comply with regulations and specifications, together with the achievement of high power density. The on-board equipment has been designed and manufactured in accordance with aeronautical regulations RTCA DO-160 and MIL-STD-704F and appropriate design considerations have been made to meet all technical requirements.

Introduction

The new trends towards a more efficient use of energy and the implementation of cleaner energy generation and distribution systems in aeronautical industry have led to the onset of More Electric Aircraft (MEA) and All Electric Aircraft (AEA) [1]. While conventional aircrafts supply power to loads through a combination of hydraulic, pneumatic, mechanical and electrical energy, MEA and AEA concepts of aircrafts aim at replacing them with only electrical systems [2]. This goal is achieved by means of the onward increase of generation and distribution of this kind of energy inside the aircraft. In this context, new generation of controlled rectifier converters are required in order to distribute electric power at HVDC level from AC generation [3].

The solution proposed in this paper converts 115 V of AC into 270 V of DC, with a nominal power capability of 15 kW, which can reach up to 22 kW. In addition, the design of this High Voltage Transformer Rectifier Unit (HVTRU) is oriented to fulfil stringent specifications of efficiency, power density, high quality of electrical performance in terms of power factor (PF), total harmonic distortion (THD) of input current, output voltage ripple, low EMI/EMC, among others. These requirements are set by MIL-STD-704F and DO-160G. An experimental and fully functional converter prototype has been developed in order to validate the design and check the compliance of specifications. The HVTRU described in this paper has an industrial projection since it is intended to be installed within Electrical Power Distribution System of a FTB2 demonstrator based on Airbus C-295. The design and development of this converter has been supported by the Clean Sky 2 programme under the Horizon 2020 framework.

Specifications

The HVTRU under design must fulfil several requirements. On the one hand, size requirement leads to a power density target of 0.57 kW/l (and 0.6 kW/kg). It should be emphasized that this target of power density takes into account the whole equipment (including cooling devices, control boards, etc.). On the other hand, HVTRU must comply with electrical requirements defined by MIL-STD-704F and also with EMI/EMC requirements defined by RTCA DO-160G. These requirements are summed up in Table 1.

Requirement	Value
Maximum weight (kg)	25
Maximum dimensions (mm)	420x250x250
Rated output power (kW)	15
Minimum efficiency	0.85 if $0.2 \cdot P_{NOM} < P$ < $0.5 \cdot P_{NOM}$ 0.9 if $P > 0.5 \cdot P_{NOM}$
Steady state output voltage limits (V)	250 to 280
Maximum ripple of output voltage (Vpp)	6
Minimum power factor	0.95
Maximum THD of input current	0.05

Table 1: Summary of main requirements.

Description of the HVTRU

HVTRU system is constituted essentially by a Power Subsystem and a Signal & Control Subsystem. Main functions of the HVTRU system are the following:

- Providing a regulated output voltage of 270 V, which complies with electrical characteristics defined in MIL-STD-704F.

- Integration of a 270 V system into an electrical system based on a 115 V_{RMS} input.
- Ensuring power quality and isolation of the DC side from the AC side. This includes limiting inrush current, minimizing THD of input current, maintaining PF as close as possible to unity and limiting load unbalance, among others.
- Detection of failures in AC power input and HVDC network. Besides control functions, HVTRU monitors several signals in order to sense abnormalities in performance.

Regarding Power Subsystem, there are several ways to accomplish power conversion from three phase AC to DC. However, considering main basic requirements, it has been decided to carry out it in two stages [4]. First, three phase AC mains is converted into an intermediate DC voltage by means of an active Power Factor Correction (PFC) stage, and then an isolated DC/DC converter reduces the voltage to 270 V. Besides AC/DC and DC/DC stages, a soft start circuit has been designed to pre-charge DC-link capacitors in a controlled way to limit as maximum as possible inrush current. See Fig. 1.

Regarding circuit topology, Vienna Rectifier, a well-known PFC topology [5], accomplishes AC/DC power conversion. It fulfils initial requirements of high efficiency and power density, as well as it allows for implementing a simple and efficient modulation technique. It is a direct three phase and three level boost-type active rectifier. It should be noted that a PFC (or active) rectifier achieves a significant reduction in THD of input current in comparison with passive rectifiers, and it also exhibits a slightly enhancement regarding PF. Vienna rectifier can also be operated at reduced output power and at the same output voltage in the case of phase loss. Thyristors have been placed ahead of boost inductors to allow DC-link capacitors charge through soft start circuit initially. Regarding PFC switches control, power MOSFETs modulation is performed by hysteresis

control, whose output binary value for gate signal is corrected depending on source voltage sign. Current and voltage controllers are based on PI structures. It is remarkably that each phase is controlled regardless of the other phases. It must be pointed out that switching frequency is variable due to the control technique implemented.

On the other hand, DC/DC conversion is carried out by a full bridge phase-shift PWM converter with center-tapped secondary winding transformer and a LC output filter [6]. Intermediate DC voltage provided by PFC stage is step-down by the transformer. Secondary transformer voltage is rectified by rectifying diodes and finally a LC filter provides a smooth regulated output voltage. Note that this topology ensures the isolation between three phase input mains and DC network generated at the output since transformer provides galvanic isolation. Besides, it penalizes sparsely PF of the whole power converter. DC/DC stage modulation, i.e. full bridge modulation, is a single bipolar PWM. Gate signals are built by comparing a carrier signal with a modulating signal generated by the DC/DC control algorithm. Frequency of the PWM has been subject to a trade-off between size of passives components (specially transformer) and overall losses.

In addition to power conversion stages, a soft start circuit has also been designed and connected to the DC-link bus in parallel to PFC, see Fig. 1. The topology is based in a diode bridge, a resistor and semiconductor switches. By this way inrush current is reduced since DC-link capacitors are charged in a controlled manner through pre-charge resistance. Switching devices allows for keeping active soft start circuit until DC-link bus reaches input line voltage. This topology achieves low losses since switches deal with low power currents, and it is more compact than solutions based in electro-mechanical power switches. Hence, it is a suited topology for this on-board application. As a counterpart, it is more complex than other soft start methods.

Fig. 1: Circuit topologies of HVTRU stages

Finally, start sequence of HVTRU follows these steps. Firstly, DC-link capacitors are charged through a soft start circuit until intermediate voltage reaches the rectified line-to-line voltage approximately. Then, soft start circuit is disconnected, thyristors of PFC are activated, and control starts to operate both PFC and DC/DC switches so that output voltage begins to increase, while DC-link continues growing up. Finally, DC-link voltage is regulated through PFC switches, and output voltage is regulated at 270 V by operating DC/DC ones.

Results

The design of the HVTRU has been validated by means of simulation model and experimental prototype of the converter. Particularly, performance of the converter has been checked varying output power in nominal input conditions. These conditions are listed in Table 2.

Parameter	Value
Input voltage, AC (V_{RMS})	115
Line frequency (Hz)	400
Input voltage phases, ($^\circ$)	0, 120, 240
Output voltage reference, DC (V)	270
Output power reference (kW)	0-15

Table 2: Operating conditions for conducted tests

Fig. 2: Prototype of the HVTRU during test performance.

As it will be outlined in this section, obtained results validate satisfactorily expected performance of the HVTRU. Table 3 lists measurement of most important figure-of-merit variables when converter provides 15 kW constantly. These results have been obtained from the prototype shown in Fig. 2. It weighs 30 kg and its dimensions are 230x430x260 mm. It achieves finally a power density of 0.5 kW/l and 0.55 kW/kg. As it can be seen in Table 3, THD of input current is below 5% in all the phases, and power factor is above 0.95. So these requirements are fulfilled in nominal conditions at rated output power. Regarding output signals, converter achieves an experimental efficiency of 92.3%, which is

higher than the minimum required for this output power. Output voltage is within the limits defined in Table 1; and the ripple, which is around 1 V_{pp}, is far below the limit of 6 V_{pp}.

Parameter	Value
Input power (kW)	15.77
Input current THD (%)	2.9
Output power (kW)	14.55
Efficiency (%)	99.3
Power factor	0.992
Output voltage, DC (V)	270.9
Output voltage ripple (V _{pp})	0.9

Table 3: Experimental results of converter performance at rated output power.

Then, converter performance under load transient condition is assessed.

Fig. 3: Output voltage measurement from experimental results under load transient condition.

Fig. 3 shows that the converter is able to regulate output voltage for tested output power range. Particularly, it falls within the limits given by Figure 16 of MIL-STD-704F, which allows output voltage to be between 250 and 280 V. This figure also shows that voltage ripple is below the maximum limit of 6 V_{p-p}.

Fig. 4: Efficiency from experimental results under load transient condition. Dashed line indicates the minimum efficiency required.

Fig.4 shows efficiency variation in relation to output power variation. It can be seen from this figure that this indicator fulfils the requirement for almost the whole range. It should be noted that efficiency values during power transients are not representative since they are calculated based on power measurements, hence only efficiency at steady state condition provides significative information. Fig. 5 shows that THD from experimental results of all the current phases are below 5% for a wide range of output power. Particularly, this indicator fulfils this requirement when output power is higher than 2.5 kW approximately. Regarding power factor, it is above 95% when output power is higher than 4 kW approximately, as Fig. 6 shows. This assures a good performance of the converter for a wide range of output power from the power factor point of view.

Fig. 5: THD from experimental results under load transition. Dashed line indicates the maximum THD allowed.

Fig. 6: Power factor from experimental results. Dashed line indicates the minimum power factor required.

Conclusions

The growing in electrical power demand is a fact in new MEA, hybrid propulsion and AEA aircrafts. As a

consequence, new designs require changes in electrical architectures and power distribution systems. In this context, optimized power converters are needed to achieve this goal. A particular application of this technology, an AC/DC power converter, has been described in this paper and experimental results obtained for an optimized prototype have been presented. The requirements are defined according to the application of this converter: the generation of a 270V DC network to feed EMAs in FTB-2 platform of C-295. A huge effort has been exerted to carry out a design oriented to fulfil aeronautical specifications in first place, and to build a working prototype that can be mounted in a real aircraft platform. After a detailed review of design criteria of power converter stages and components selection, as well as a brief description of implemented modulation and control techniques for all the stages, experimental results are presented.

The converter performance fulfils initial requirements under the operating conditions considered, for almost the whole range of output power. Experimental efficiency and prototype power density are major concerns of a power converter in aeronautical application, since cooling possibilities are limited, as well as physical space for electrical and electronic equipment. Regarding power density, the final result is very close to the initial target of 0.6 kW/l. As for efficiency, it is above 90% for a wide range of output power. Besides, THD of input current is below the imposed 5% in almost the whole range of output power. Low THD and high PF allow for not only an efficient converter performance but also a better utilization of the power source (i.e. aircraft generators). The review of environmental specifications compliance is beyond the scope of this paper.

References

- 1 X. Roboam et al, More Electricity in the Air, IEEE Ind. Electron. Mag., 2012, Vol.6, pp.6-17.
- 2 P. Wheeler et al, The More Electric Aircraft: Technology and challenges, IEEE Electrif. Mag., 2014, Vol.2, pp.6-12.
- 3 B. Sarlioglu et al, More Electric Aircraft : Review, Challenges and Opportunities for Commercial Aircraft Transport, IEEE Trans. Transp. Electrif., 2015, vol.1, pp. 54-64.
- 4 O. Garcia et al, Single Phase Power Factor Correction : A survey, IEEE Trans. Power Electron., 2003, vol. 18, pp. 749-755.
- 5 J.W. Kolar et al, The Essence of Three-Phase PFC Rectifier Systems – Part I, IEEE Trans. Power Electron., 2013, vol. 28, pp. 176-198.
- 6 U. Badstuebner, Ultra-High Performance Telecom DC-DC Converter, Ph.D. Thesis, ETH Zurich, 2011